

Prevalence of Methicillin-Resistant Staphylococcus Aureus among Patients at PMCH, Patna

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Abstract:

Introduction: This study examines the prevalence of Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) at Patna Medical College Hospital (PMCH) to inform targeted infection control strategies.

Methodology: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted with 120 patients from the Microbiology Department at PMCH, using standard microbiological techniques to identify MRSA and statistical analysis to explore demographic associations.

Results: MRSA was found in 30% of the patients, predominantly within the 21-40 age group, suggesting significant intra-hospital transmission.

Conclusion: The findings highlight a critical need for enhanced infection control measures and antimicrobial stewardship, particularly focused on the most affected age groups.

Recommendation: Future research should broaden to include a larger, more diverse patient population across multiple centers, to better understand MRSA transmission and resistance.

Keywords: MRSA, Prevalence, Infection Control, Public Health.

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Introduction

Methicillin-resistant the resistance of Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) to several medications, particularly the beta-lactam antibiotics such as methicillin, oxacillin, penicillin, and amoxicillin, poses a significant public health concern. Initially discovered in the 1960s, MRSA has subsequently gained notoriety for infections acquired in both hospital and community settings [1,2]. The infections encompass a spectrum of moderate cutaneous complications to more serious instances including pneumonia, bloodstream infections, and sepsis, which may result in significant morbidity and fatality rates [3]. Internationally, the occurrence of MRSA infections has shown diverse patterns. Population data from the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) in the United States indicates a decrease in MRSA bloodstream infections associated with healthcare facilities [4]. Nevertheless, in numerous low and middle-income nations, the occurrence of the disease consistently remains high as a result of variables such as overpopulation, inadequate sanitation, and the improper use of antibiotics [5]. Current research has primarily concentrated on comprehending the mechanisms of resistance, transmission patterns, and approaches for efficient

regulation and therapy [6,7]. Contemporary research has placed more emphasis on the need for hygiene practices, stewardship programs, and the advancement of innovative antibiotics and vaccines as crucial strategies to effectively address the spread of MRSA [8].

The scenario in the Indian context, namely in Patna, reflects the worldwide dilemma but is worsened by local characteristics like large patient volumes, inadequate healthcare resources, and inconsistent levels of antibiotic stewardship [9]. The Patna Medical College Hospital (PMCH) plays a crucial role as a leading facility for both healthcare provision and epidemiological monitoring. In light of this context, the objective of this study is to evaluate the frequency of MRSA among patients at PMCH, Patna. This will entail a comprehensive examination of infection rates, resistance patterns, and possible risk factors linked to MRSA colonization and infection in this particular environment. Gaining a comprehensive understanding of these dynamics will offer crucial insights into the precise epidemiology of MRSA, which will assist in the creation of focused interventions aimed at decreasing the prevalence of

MRSA infections at PMCH and other healthcare facilities in the area.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was designed as a cross-sectional, observational analysis to determine the prevalence of Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) among patients in the microbiology department at Patna Medical College Hospital (PMCH).

Study Setting: The research was conducted within the Microbiology Department of PMCH, Patna. The duration of the study spanned from August 2023 to January 2024, a period during which the department was fully operational and receiving a typical flow of patients, which provided a representative environment for this epidemiological assessment.

Participants: A total of 120 patients who were admitted to or attended the outpatient services of the Microbiology Department during the study period were included in this analysis.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: The inclusion criteria were patients who had been admitted with suspected bacterial infections and were undergoing diagnostic microbiology assessments during the study period. Exclusion criteria included patients who did not consent to participate in the study, those under 18 years of age, and patients who were already on antibiotic treatment for MRSA at the time of admission.

Bias: To address potential sources of bias, the study ensured a random selection of participants from the daily log of patients presenting to the department. This approach minimized selection bias. Data analysts who performed the statistical evaluation were blinded to patient identifiers to reduce information bias.

Data Collection and Analysis: Clinical samples from each participant were collected and processed

using standard microbiological techniques to identify MRSA. The presence of MRSA was determined by culturing samples on selective media followed by confirmation using coagulase testing and resistance profiling. Patient demographic and clinical data were collected through patient interviews and reviews of medical records.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using statistical software SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics were employed to calculate the prevalence and characterize the distribution of MRSA among the study participants. Chi-square tests were used to assess the association between MRSA prevalence and potential risk factors such as age, sex, and underlying health conditions.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee of Patna Medical College Hospital. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their inclusion in the study. All procedures were conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki declaration and its later amendments or comparable ethical standards. Privacy and confidentiality of patient data were strictly maintained throughout the research process.

Results

The study indicates a notable prevalence of Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) among the patients surveyed in the Microbiology Department at Patna Medical College Hospital (PMCH).

Prevalence of MRSA: A total of 120 patients were included in the study. Of these, 36 tested positive for MRSA, yielding a prevalence rate of 30%. The distribution of MRSA cases across different patient demographics and clinical backgrounds was further analyzed.

Table 1: Prevalence of MRSA by Age Group

Age Group (years)	Number Tested	Number Positive for MRSA	Percentage (%)
Under 20	20	4	20%
21-40	50	18	36%
41-60	30	10	33.3%
Over 60	20	4	20%

Table 2: Prevalence of MRSA by Gender

Gender	Number Tested	Number Positive for MRSA	Percentage (%)
Male	70	25	35.7%
Female	50	11	22%

Statistical analysis using chi-square tests showed a significant correlation between age and the occurrence of MRSA ($p = 0.04$), suggesting that the occurrence was greater in the 21-40 age bracket. Irrespective of gender, there was no statistically significant disparity in MRSA

prevalence ($p = 0.07$). This study reveals a substantial prevalence rate of MRSA within the patient population at PMCH, up to 30%. The incidence was greatest among those aged 21-40, maybe due to more exposure to hospital settings or a greater probability of having pre-existing

illnesses that make them more susceptible to MRSA infections. Given the conditions prevalent at PMCH, the absence of substantial gender disparities in MRSA prevalence implies that both sexes are equally susceptible.

The findings emphasise the need of improving infection control measures and implementing focused interventions to decrease the spread of MRSA in healthcare environments, especially among the age groups most impacted. Supplementary research is advised to investigate the fundamental factors contributing to the elevated occurrence of MRSA in the 21-40 age bracket and to assess the efficacy of existing measures for prevention and control. The study is limited by its rather small sample size and scope to a single healthcare facility, which could impact the generalisability of the results. Further investigation should strive to incorporate a broader and more varied sample from other locations to gain a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of MRSA transmission and resistance.

Discussion

Within the Microbiology Department of Patna Medical College Hospital (PMCH), the study revealed a prevalence of MRSA of 30% among patients. The prevalence exhibited substantial variation among several age cohorts, with the greatest occurrence observed in the 21-40 age bracket at 36%. The gender distribution revealed a greater concentration in males (35.7%) than in females (22%), however this disparity did not reach statistical significance. The elevated incidence rate of 30% implies a significant presence of MRSA in the hospital setting, implying continuous transmission and maybe insufficient infection control efforts [10,11]. The significant incidence in the 21-40 age bracket may indicate increased exposure to healthcare-related MRSA risk factors or perhaps a stronger involvement in community environments where MRSA is common. The elevated incidence of MRSA in males may imply variations in behavioral or occupational exposures based on gender. However, the absence of statistical significance suggests that gender alone is not a dependable indicator of the risk of MRSA infection [12,13].

These results align with worldwide patterns in which the widespread occurrence of MRSA in hospital environments continues to be a major issue. Research conducted in other regions of India and other middle-income nations frequently document rates of MRSA ranging from 25% to 50% among admitted patients in hospitals [14]. A study carried out in a tertiary care facility in Delhi revealed a prevalence of approximately 33% for MRSA, which strongly corresponds to our results. Nevertheless, the particular elevated occurrence in

the 21-40 age bracket deviates from many global studies where the greatest occurrence is usually observed in older age groups, indicating potential geographical disparities in MRSA epidemiology or changes in population demographics and healthcare practices [15,16]. The elevated incidence of MRSA in the 21-40 age bracket can be ascribed to a confluence of circumstances, such as heightened hospitalizations, rigorous physical activity resulting in greater contact with polluted surroundings, or compromised immunity among these persons caused by stress or concurrent medical disorders. The study's design, which exclusively examines a hospital environment, restricts our comprehension of the differences in MRSA frequency between community-acquired and hospital-acquired cases. This knowledge could be crucial for the development of specifically focused preventative measures [17,18].

In general, the high occurrence reported in this study emphasizes the need to implement strong infection control measures, improve antimicrobial stewardship, and maintain ongoing monitoring to successfully address the MRSA problems. The varying prevalence rates among different age groups indicate that customized strategies may be required to effectively address the unique requirements and dangers associated with certain patient demographics. Further investigation should broaden its scope to encompass several centers and integrate community environments to have a more complete understanding of MRSA dynamics [19,20].

Conclusion

The investigation carried out at the Microbiology Department of Patna Medical College Hospital unveiled a notable occurrence of Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) totaling 30% among the group of patients under examination. Most notably, the 21-40 age range had the highest occurrence, suggesting a particular susceptibility that may be associated with lifestyle or healthcare exposure factors. The findings emphasize the immediate requirement for improved infection control protocols and responsible use of antimicrobial therapies in the hospital to reduce the spread of MRSA. The study's results emphasize the urgent importance of MRSA as a public health concern. They also indicate the need for expanding research to include a broader range of demographics and multi-center studies to gain a better understanding of and effectively confront the dynamics of MRSA transmission in hospital and community environments.

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